

1 **A cryogel-based bioreactor for water treatment applications**

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7

8 *Abstract*

9 *The aim of this study was to develop and test a non-diffusion limited, high cell density*
10 *bioreactor for biodegradation of various phenol derivatives. The bioreactor was obtained*
11 *using a straightforward one-step preparation method using cryostructuration and direct cross-*
12 *linking of bacteria into a 3D structured (sponge-like) macroporous cryogel composite material*
13 *consisting of 11.6% (by mass) cells and 1.2-1.7% polymer, with approximately 87% water (in*
14 *the material pores). The macroporous cryogel composite material, composed of live bacteria,*
15 *has pore sizes in the range of 20-150 μm (confirmed by SEM and Laser Scanning Confocal*
16 *Microscopy). The enzymatic activity of bacteria within the cryogel structure and the effect of*
17 *freezing on the viability of the cross-linked cells was estimated by MTT assay. Cryogels based*
18 *on *Pseudomonas mendocina*, *Rhodococcus koreensis* and *Acinetobacter radioresistens* were*
19 *exploited for the effective bioremediation of phenol and m-cresol, and to a lesser extent 2-*
20 *chlorophenol and 4-chlorophenol, utilising these phenolic contaminants in water as their only*
21 *source of carbon. For evaluation of treatment scalability the bioreactors were prepared in*
22 *plastic “Kaldnes” carriers to improve their mechanical properties and allow application in*
23 *batch or fluidised bed water treatment modes.*

24

25 *Keywords: bacteria immobilisation, bioremediation, phenol, cresol, chlorophenols.*

26

27 **Introduction**

28 Bioremediation of contaminated water and soil is an effective approach for the removal of
29 xenobiotics and other contaminants from the environment. It utilises the ability of
30 microorganisms to degrade, or reduce the toxicity or mobility of, specific target compounds,
31 and is considered one of the more efficient, cost effective and eco-friendly remediation
32 methods. An extensive body of research has focused on utilising this method for a wide range
33 of contaminants, including pesticides, heavy metals and aromatic hydrocarbons. For water
34 treatment applications, the use of bacteria immobilised on a substrate has numerous
35 advantages over the use of bacterial suspensions, such as higher biomass density, high
36 metabolic activity, and higher resistance to toxic chemicals, allowing continuous operation
37 processes(Villegas et al., 2016; Chen et al., 2007; Börner et al., 2014; Zaushitsyna et al.,
38 2014; Gonzalez et al., 2001). Several bacterial immobilisation methods have been developed
39 and various synthetic and natural carriers are known(Anku et al., 2017; Dzionek et al., 2016;
40 Chiellini et al., 1999). The degree of bacterial immobilisation depends on the structure, pore
41 size and surface area of the support, as well as the nature of the material (i.e. its hydrophobi-
42 city, charge, etc.) and environmental conditions, such as pH, and temperature(Hailei et al.,
43 2016; Cortez et al., 2017). Adsorption (to the substrate) or biofilm formation is often a long
44 process however and represents the main cost, and one of the major limitations, of
45 bioremediation using immobilised bacteria. Immobilisation methods via encapsulation of
46 cells inside a polymer matrix (e.g. polyvinylalcohol (PVA), carrageenan and agar gel) can
47 produce relatively high cell densities (Cortez et al., 2017; El-Naas et al., 2009; Sinha et al.,
48 2011), however such materials tend to have diffusion limitations due to the use of high
49 concentrations of polymer (6-10%) which coats the cells and restricts their interaction with
50 contaminated water. Polyethylenimine(PEI) derivatives are a popular immobilising agent

51 which have restricted application for bacterial immobilisation due to high toxicity issues
52 (Virgen-Ortiz et al., 2017; Milović et al., 2005). In this study, we suggest a novel approach to
53 the design of immobilised bacteria-based bioreactors for water treatment applications. To
54 overcome existing limitations, a minimum concentration of polymers (1.2%) was used for
55 cross-linking an 11.6% wt. suspension of bacterial cells in a 3D macroporous bacterial
56 “sponge”, produced via a facile one-step cryostructuring process. The morphology of the
57 developed macroporous materials, based on *Acinetobacter radioresistens*(*Acn*), *Pseudomonas*
58 *mendocina*(*Pse*) and *Rhodococcus koreensis*(*Rho*) with six commonly used immobilising
59 polymers (and their combinations – PVA, PEI, chitosan, Gellan Gum and glutaraldehyde),
60 was characterised and the materials tested for their bioremediation efficiency against phenol
61 derivative compounds (phenol, *m*-(*p*-)cresols and CPs).

62

63 **2. Materials and Methods.**

64 2.1 Synthesis of aldehyde containing polymers

65 A combination of PVA-al and PEI-al was utilised as a cross-linking agent for bacteria (*Pse*,
66 *Acn* and *Rho*). Polyvinyl alcohol was modified with aldehyde groups (PVA-al). Briefly, 0.6
67 mL of GA (50% v/v) was added to a 2% acidified PVA solution in distilled water. Note that
68 the PVA modification is inefficient at neutral conditions. The reaction was terminated by pH
69 adjustment to pH 6-7.5. Unreacted GA was removed by dialysis utilising a dialysis bag (cut off
70 12 kDa) against water. Polyethyleneimine (PEI) was modified in similar manner by adding 8.8
71 mL of GA (20 v/v %) to 2% polymer solution in water. The pH was adjusted to 7 prior to GA
72 addition to avoid aldol condensation of aldehyde under alkaline conditions, and therefore to
73 achieve a more consistent chemical composition of the polymer. The reaction mixture was
74 incubated under stirring for 2h at room temperature, the pH adjusted to seven, and then the
75 mixture was dialysed against water (a dialysis bag cut off 1 kDa).The obtained polymer

76 solution was filtered through a 0.45µm membrane and stored at 4 °C until subsequent use. The
77 concentration of the polymer in the solution was estimated by using a freeze drying method
78 and measuring the final dry weight of the polymer.

79 2.2 Characterisation of polymers

80 FT-IR analysis of freeze dried polymers (PVA-al and PVA and PEI-al) was performed
81 using a Bruker Alpha P instrument with attenuated total reflectance. Spectra were acquired in
82 the 4000–400 cm⁻¹ range with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹ for 24 scans to confirm the presence of
83 aldehyde groups.

84 ¹H-NMR spectra of solutions of PEI-al and PVA-al (10 mg/mL) and non-modified PEI
85 and PVA dissolved in D₂O were produced using a Bruker DSX 400 MHz spectrometer.

86 The molecular weight distribution of the modified polymers (PVA-al and PEI-al) was
87 estimated via photon correlation spectroscopy, using a particle sizer (Zeta sizer 3000 HAS,
88 Malvern Instruments Ltd., Malvern, Worcestershire, UK). Analysis was performed at 25°C
89 using a measurement angle of 90°, with 11 runs for each measurement (n=3). Zeta potential
90 measurements of the polymers were also carried out (in triplicate) to estimate surface charge,
91 using a Zeta sizer 3000 HAS (Malvern Instruments Ltd., Malvern, Worcestershire, UK, 1mL
92 aqueous dip cell, cuvette DTS1070 (n=3)).

93 2.3 3D macroporous bioreactor preparation.

94 A significantly improved streamlined preparation method for 3D macroporous bioreactors
95 (here termed cryobacteria reactors, or CBRs prepared within a special plastic carrier) is
96 presented compared to one recently published by our group (Al-Jwaid et al., 2018). Briefly,
97 120 mL of media after cell cultivation OD₆₀₀ 1.0-1.4 was centrifuged at 10 000 rpm for 10
98 minutes at 4 °C. According to literature data for *Pseudomonas sp.*, one unit OD₆₀₀ corresponds
99 to 2.08x10⁸ CFU and has a cell density of 2.085 mg/mL (Kim et al., 2012). The wet weight of
100 the pelleted cells was calculated accordingly. For calculation of the bacterial cell density of

101 *Rho* and *Acn* the following ratio was applied: an OD₆₀₀ of one resulted in a cell wet weight of
102 1.7 g/L and 0.39 g/L of dry weight, respectively (Glazyrina et al., 2010). The pelleted cells
103 (wet mass of 0.29g) were mixed gently with 2.5 mL of cross-linker solution in a phosphate
104 buffer(PB) (pH 7.2) (or water or PB and 2% glucose) at various ratios (PEI-al-PVA-al 0.6:0.6%
105 or 1.7% PVA-al), avoiding generation of bubbles in the cell suspension (all percentages shown
106 in material compositions are based on % mass in the final composite material). This solution
107 was transferred into a glass tube (diameter 9 mm) and frozen rapidly in a cryobath at -12 °C,
108 and kept at that condition for 3 days. CBRs based on *Pse* (11.6 %)-PVA-al-PEI-al 0.6:0.6%
109 (Cryo-*Pse*), *Rho* (11.6 %)-PVA-al-PEI-al 0.6:0.6% (Cryo-*Rho*), *Acn* (11.6 %)-PVA-al-PEI-al
110 0.6:0.6% (Cryo-*Acn*) obtained were thawed at room temperature and used for bioremediation
111 process testing directly.

112 Cryogels without bacteria were prepared according to the aforementioned procedure and were
113 based on the combination of PVA-al-PEI-al 0.6:0.6 % or PVA-al-PEI-al 1:1 and PVA-al 1.7%.
114 These cryogels were used as a control to estimate nonspecific adsorption of phenol derivatives
115 by the polymer matrix, and for physico-chemical characterisation.

116 Cryogels prepared from a combination of polymers PVA, PEI, chitosan(CHI), Gellan
117 Gum(Gel) and glutaraldehyde(GA), as well as only GA(0.5%) and were prepared analogously
118 to the above mentioned procedure. Prior to the addition of chitosan to the cells suspension, a
119 stock solution was dissolved in 1% acetic acid. The stock solution of Gellan Gum (1.5%) was
120 prepared in distilled water. CryoPho-PVA-PEI-GA 11.6:1:1:0.25%, CryoPho-PVA-PEI-GA
121 11.6:0.6:0.6:0.25%, CryoPho-CHI-GA 11.6:1:0.25%, CryoPho-Gel:PVA-al 11.6:0.3:1.0%,
122 CryoPho-Gel:PVA-al 11.6:0.52:0.32%, CryoPho-Gel 11.6:0.5% CryoPse-Gel 11.6:0.5% were
123 prepared at -12 °C and their bioremediation activity tested.

124 Cryobacteria reactors based on *Acn*, *Pse* and *Rho* were also prepared in polypropylene
125 'Kaldnes' carriers (d=11mm and h=7mm, with the volume of cell suspension 0.55 mL) using

126 the same method as detailed above. Incorporation of the CBRs into plastic carriers improves
127 their mechanical stability and decreases the possibility of mechanical damage under intensive
128 mixing or application of high flow rate, or during the recharging of solutions between
129 bioremediation cycles (Önnby et al., 2010, Rusten, et al., 2006). CBRs based on: *Pse* (pellet
130 of 100 mL, OD₆₀₀ 1.06 or 221mg), PVA-al-PEI-al 0.6:0.6% (CBR-*Pse*); *Rho* (pellet of 100
131 mL, OD₆₀₀ 1.4 or 238mg), PVA-al-PEI-al 0.6:0.6% (CBR-*Rho*); and *Acn* (adapted on the TSB
132 plate to 2CP) (pellet of 100 mL, OD₆₀₀ 1.04 or 170mg) PVA-al-PEI-al 0.6:0.6% (CBR-*Acn*)
133 were prepared in PB with final concentration of bacteria of 11.6%. The bacterial suspension
134 was mixed with cross-linker and placed into a glass tube 11.5 mm in diameter containing plastic
135 carriers. The glass tube was frozen at -12 °C for 3 days. Then CBR samples in the carrier (*Pse*
136 PVA-al-PEI-al 11.6:0.6:0.6% (CBR-*Pse*) (44mg of cells/carrier), *Rho*-PVA-al-PEI-al
137 11.6:0.6:0.6% (CBR-*Rho*) (47.6mg of cells/carrier), and *Acn*-PVA-al-PEI-al 11.6:0.6:0.6%
138 (CBR-*Acn*) (34mg of cells/carrier)) were thawed at room temperature and used for
139 bioremediation process testing directly.

140 The number of live bacteria in the CBRs was assessed using a MTT assay(Hao et al., 2002),
141 following standard methods.

142 2.4 3D macroporous bioreactor characterisation

143 The elastic moduli of the cryogel bacteria reactors (CBRs) were studied using a TA-
144 XT2 instrument (Stable Micro Systems, Godalming, Surrey, UK). The compression test was
145 performed at room temperature. The cryogels were prepared with a diameter of 8 mm and
146 height of 9 mm. Samples were compressed up to a deformation level of 50 % at a speed of 0.05
147 mm/s. The elastic modulus was calculated at a deformation of 5% using the equation

$$148 \quad E = (F/S)/(\Delta h/h)$$

149 where E is the elastic modulus (Pa), F is the force applied (N), S is the cross-sectional area of
150 the sample (m^2), Δh is the height (m) at compression, and h is the original height (m) (Kirsebom
151 et al. 2013).

152 Three samples were used for each type of composite cryogel.

153 Scanning electronic microscopy (SEM) images were obtained using a Zeiss Sigma field
154 emission gun SEM (Zeiss NTS). Slices of CBRs with thickness of 1-2 mm were washed with
155 PBS, and then samples were fixed in 5% v/v GA in PBS overnight following by washing with
156 PBS and water. Then, slices were frozen at -20 °C overnight and freeze dried in a Christ
157 ALPHA 2-4 freeze-dryer for 24 hours. Finally, freeze-dried samples were coated with a layer
158 of platinum using a Quorum (Q150TES) coater.

159 Confocal laser scan microscopy (CLSM) images were obtained using a Leica TCS SP5
160 using objective lens x10, x20, x40 and x63. CBRs were fixed in 5 v/v % GA in PBS buffer
161 overnight and then cut into slices with a thickness of 1 mm. Samples were washed with distilled
162 water to remove non-crosslinked bacteria and stained with Rhodamine B solution overnight.
163 Unbound Rhodamine B was washed out with water. Another batch of CBRs was stained with
164 FITC solution (0.02 mg/mL in sodium phosphate buffer, pH 9.0) overnight. Non-reacted FITC
165 was washed out with water. The 488 and 530 nm excitation and emission wavelengths were
166 applied. Images were produced by optical sectioning in the xy-planes along the z-axis with 30-
167 70 optical sections with 1 μm intervals.

168 Evaluation of the viability of crosslinked bacteria within the cryogel was performed using
169 standard Live/Dead assay. Cryogels were cut into thin slices with a thickness of 1 mm and
170 washed out with NaCl 0.9% solution to remove uncross-linked cells. Samples were stained
171 using Live/Dead Bac Light kit containing SYTO 9 stain at wavelength 480/500 nm and
172 propidium iodide at wavelength 490/635 nm for 15 minutes at room temperature under dark
173 conditions (according to the protocol of the LIVE/DEAD® Bacterial viability kit of staining).

174 2.5 Bioremediation by suspensions of bacteria and CBRs.

175 The degradation of phenol, *m*-cresol and 2-chlorophenol (2-CP) or 4-chlorophenol (4-CP) by
176 a suspension of non-crosslinked bacteria and by various CBRs was studied. In the case of
177 bioremediation by a bacterial suspension(planktonic state) the same amount of bacteria
178 (measured based on OD₆₀₀) as applied in the cryogel preparation was used . Forty mL of phenol
179 derivative were added to the pellet of bacteria in a sterile 50 mL plastic falcon tube. The tube
180 was regularly opened for sampling (207 μL at each time point) under sterile conditions. Note
181 that the tube contained approximately 10 mL of air. The tubes were shaken at 150 rpm at 30°C
182 in the dark(dynamic mode). The number of bacteria in the solution during the bioremediation
183 process was monitored by measurement of OD₆₀₀ at each sampling point.

184 CBRs were placed in 40 mL of phenol derivative (phenol, *m*-cresol, 2-CP and 4-CP) in
185 minimum salt media (MSM) buffer at pH 7.0 in a static mode(without additional shaking) at
186 30°C. Control sterile solutions (phenol, *m*-cresol, 2-CP and 4-CP in MSM) were prepared under
187 the same conditions and tested to estimate stability against degradation over time in a static
188 mode. Nonspecific adsorption of 4-CP on the PEI-al-PVA-al and PVA-al control cryogels
189 (without bacteria, see section 2.3) was evaluated in MSM at 30°C in dynamic mode. Due to
190 observable biofilm formation in the glass bottle during the bioremediation process, each cycle
191 was performed in a new set of sterile bottles to eliminate the effect of biofilm formation on the
192 following bioremediation cycles. The efficiency of the bioreactors was calculated as
193 previously discussed (Börner et al. 2014), based on the change of contaminant concentration
194 at a given time point (48 and 220h) divided by the experimental duration (i.e. the number of
195 hours of bioreactor or bacteria exposure to the target contaminant) (mg/L/h) according to the
196 equation: $\text{Efficiency}=(C_0-C_t)/t$

197 where C_0 is initial concentration, C_t concentration at a time point.

198 The error was calculated according to the standard equation:

199 Error = (StDev(A1:Ai))/($\sqrt{\text{COUNT}(A1:Ai)}$), where StDev is standard deviation,
200 COUNT(A1:Ai) number of replicates.

201 **3. Results and discussion**

202 3.1 Cryobacteria reactor (CBR) preparation and characterisation

203 In our recent work we used combinations of polymers GA(0.385%); GA & PVA
204 (0.385:0.77%); PVA-al & PEI-al(0.385:0.46%); PVA-al & PEI-al(0.77:0.19%), keeping the
205 concentration of bacteria at 23% (by mass) for preparation of cryogels(Al-Jwaid et al., 2018).
206 Here, to select the best performing bioremediation system, cryobacteria reactors based on three
207 bacterial strains and six immobilising polymers (and their combinations) were screened. PVA
208 and PEI modified with aldehyde groups were used as cross-linkers. The presence of aldehyde
209 group in the modified polymers was confirmed by FTIR and $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectroscopy (Fig. S2(a-
210 c)). As expected the zeta potentials of the PVA and PVA-al were close to zero, illustrating the
211 electroneutrality of the cross-linking agent, whereas PEI-al showed a zeta potential of 32 ± 4
212 mV indicating that the cross-linker is positively charged (Fig. S3) and therefore can
213 additionally interact with cell membranes via electrostatic interactions. Additionally, cryogels
214 with chitosan and Gellan Gum were prepared to analyse the bacteria immobilisation as result
215 of electrostatic interaction between the cell membrane and these polymers.

216 In previous work, bacteria capable of the bioremediation of phenol were immobilised on
217 cryogel surfaces in three steps; overall the cryogel preparation and the following biofilm
218 formation was completed in 10 days and required the use of additional equipment such as UV
219 lamps (400 W)(Satchanska et al. 2015). The subsequent bioreactor contained a large amount
220 of bulk polymer leading to issues of disposal after its use, and this technique therefore is less
221 practical for industrial application.

222 Here, suspensions of *P. mendocina* (*Pse*), *R. koreensis* (*Rho*) and *A. radioresistens* (*Acn*) (11.6
223 w/w%) were cross-linked by a combination of PEI-al-PVA-al (0.6-0.6 w/w%) prepared in PB

224 in a one-step cryostructuration process. When the suspension of cells and cross-linker freezes
225 under semi-frozen conditions (-12°C) ice crystals form, which leads to phase separation of the
226 cells and the cross-linker suspension and ice (Fig. 1). The growing ice crystals expel all solutes
227 and bacteria into a non-frozen liquid microphase, which remains non-frozen even at -12 °C
228 (Kirsebom et al., 2013). The bacteria and cross-linker therefore concentrate in the thin non-
229 frozen liquid microphase, and the bacteria become densely packed and cross-linked by
230 functional polymers interacting with their cell membranes. Thawing of samples results in the
231 melting of the ice crystals, producing water-filled voids - pores. This results in a 3D structured
232 macroporous material, formed in a one-step preparation method, with the pore walls composed
233 mostly of bacterial cells tightly attached to each other, surrounding a well-developed system of
234 interconnected large pores with size 20-150 μm (Fig. 2). The obtained cryogels were self-
235 supporting, mechanically stable (Fig. S4), and withstand processing in a static and a dynamic
236 mode (i.e. shaking at 150 rpm) for at least 4 weeks (Fig. S5(A-D)).

237 Rapid aggregation of cells was observed upon addition of glutaraldehyde. The Cryo-
238 *Acn*-PVA-al has no obvious cells in the cryogel wall due to use of a relatively high
239 concentration of cross-linking agent (1.7%, Fig. 2i(A-C)). It was observed that the change of
240 composition of the buffer did not change the morphology of the material significantly (Fig.
241 2ii). Nevertheless, the use of PB or PB & glucose has advantages compared to cryogels
242 prepared in pure water, as these decrease the osmotic stress during cryogel preparation and
243 keep the pH constant.

244 To visualise the efficiency of mixing of the bacteria with the polymer, as well as to assess the
245 distribution and amount of live cells, CBRs were stained with Live/Dead stains. The hydrogel
246 based on Gellan was characterised by the absence of large pores in the structure of the
247 composite hydrogels, and a homogeneous distribution of cells within the material (Fig. 3(E-
248 H)). A strong fluorescence background due to electrostatic binding of the positively charged

249 dyes with the negatively charged polymer can be observed under CLSM. Nevertheless, at
250 magnification x100 the images clearly distinguish between cells and background (Fig. 3(H)).
251 The material has a predominantly microporous structure however and therefore can be used
252 only in batch application in a dynamic mode (Fig. 3(E-H)). We focused on preparation and
253 assessment of the bioremediation activity of macroporous materials, which potentially could
254 be used additionally in a flow through mode.

255 Some of the key beneficial properties of cryogels relate to their elastic strength, flexibility and
256 shape recovery. In our recent study we comprehensively investigated the rheological properties
257 of cryogels based on bacteria (Al-Jwaid et al., 2018), however the elastic modulus was not
258 measured. The elastic modulus of the cryogels *Acn*-PVA-al (1.0%) and *Acn*-PVA-al-PEI-al
259 (1.0:0.25(%)) was 3.52 ± 0.7 and 4.64 ± 0.1 kPa, respectively. These values were similar to
260 those previously reported for cryogels made of *E.coli* and activated polyethylenimine, which
261 had an elastic modulus of 3.1 ± 0.39 kPa,(Zaushitsyna et al., 2014) or porous material *C.*
262 *saccharolyticus* cross-linked by glutaraldehyde which showed a modulus in the range 8 - 29
263 kPa (Kirsebom et al., 2009). Our data were also comparable with the elastic modulus of
264 cryogels based on polymers such as enzymatically cross-linked casein (1.3 - 7 kPa) and gelatin
265 (0.95 - 1.9 kPa)(Kirsebom et al., 2013) or combinations of polymeric cross-linking agent
266 aldehyde dextran and gelatin (0.6-2.8 kPa), respectively(Berillo and Volkova 2014). Cryo-
267 Rho-PVA-al-PEI-al-Gel (11.6:0.5:0.6:0.3(%)), Cryo-Rho-PVA-al-Gel (11.6:1.0:0.3(%))
268 prepared in water, and Cryo-Rho-PVA-al-Gel (11.6:1.0:0.3(%)) formed in phosphate buffer
269 had elastic moduli of 16.1 ± 1.7 , 87.7 ± 16.3 , 28.7 ± 17.0 kPa, respectively. As expected, an
270 increase of CHI concentration from 0.5 to 1.0% at constant polymer cross-linking mass ratio
271 (2:1) led to a significant increase in the toughness of the material (Fig. S4). Cryogels based on
272 *Rho*(11.6%) in combination with polymers CHI-GA 0.5:0.25% and CHI-GA 1.0:0.5%, PEI-
273 GA1.0:0.25%, and 1.0:0.5%, PEI-PVA-GA 1.0:1.0:0.25% showed an elastic modulus of 34.7

274 ± 15.5 ; 1955 ± 268 ; 12.4 ± 8 ; 10.8 ± 0.9 ; 7.2 ± 1.5 kPa, respectively. As expected the highest
275 elasticity modulus was found for samples based on CHI, which is related to the rigid structure
276 of this polysaccharide. The incorporation of Gel to the structure significantly improves the
277 mechanical properties of the material due to formation of a physical gel. In figure S4 an
278 illustrated comparison of the elastic properties of composite cryogels based on *Rhodococcus*
279 *sp* is given.

280 The analysis of live and dead bacteria using live/dead kit indicates that most of the bacteria
281 after cross-linking were viable (stained green, Fig. 3(e-h)) even after undergoing freeze-
282 thawing conditions during the cryogelation process. Potentially, cryogenic conditions
283 (particularly ice-crystal formation) as well as the cross-linker and the osmotic stress itself could
284 damage the bacterial cells and reduce viable cell numbers. To distinguish the potential harmful
285 effects of the polymer cross-linker from those caused by cryogenic conditions the experiments
286 were performed at 4°C / -12°C , respectively. Incubation of *Rho* suspension in the solution of
287 PBS containing 0.25 or 0.5 % of GA (negative control) at 4°C for 24 h led to a significant
288 decrease in the number of live bacteria, to 27 % and 22 % of initial numbers respectively, due
289 to the toxicity of GA. The use of PEI-al (0.365 w/v %) in PBS resulted in a 25 % of live *Acn*
290 bacteria. PEI-al was more toxic compared to unmodified PEI (where 50 % of bacteria
291 survived). PVA-al 1.2 % in PBS buffer at 4°C revealed a high survival of *Acn* (92.4 %)
292 compared to a bacterial suspension stored in phosphate buffer without polymer (100 %)
293 (positive control) (Table S1).

294 The issue of the relatively high toxicity of PEI-al was overcome by the use of a combination
295 of nontoxic PVA-al with PEI-al, leading to 72.5% active bacteria. The use of only PVA-al led
296 to formation of a material with low water permeability, while using a combination of PVA-al-
297 PEI-al (1:1) resulted in formation of a material with desirable porosity characteristics and
298 mechanical properties. A small amount of glucose, which acted as a cryoprotector and

299 potentially as a source of carbon, was added to the bacterial suspension to decrease the effect
300 of cell bacteria damage due to ice crystal formation and osmotic shock (Moslemy et al., 2002).
301 PVA-al 1.2% dissolved in PBS buffer in the presence of 2 % glucose showed some growth of
302 the *Acn* bacteria at 4°C (109 %) after 24h (Table S1). The frozen suspension of *Acn* in PVA-al
303 1.2 % and PBS buffer with 2 % glucose added showed 88.6 % survival from the initial number
304 of cells. Thus, a decrease of 11.4% in live bacteria was related to bacterial damage by growing
305 ice crystals. The effect of 1.0% glucose in PBS buffer on bacterial viability was also
306 investigated (Table S1). The incubation of *Pse* suspension in PBS buffer containing 1.0%
307 glucose over 24h at 4°C led to a 13.8% decrease in cell populations compared to the PBS buffer.
308 The presence of glucose did not significantly improve the viability of *Pse* during the
309 cryogelation process either (Table S1). It can be concluded that addition of glucose in
310 combination with PVA-al-PEI-al (1:1) did not significantly improve the survival of the bacteria
311 or even had some negative effect on *Pse*, but conversely it had a positive effect on *Acn* during
312 incubation for 24h at 4°C. It can also be concluded that the 23% *Pse* bacteria population
313 decrease observed after incubation at 4°C for 24h was due to cumulative toxicity from the
314 PVA-al-PEI-al polymers, while the 53% loss of bacteria after cryogelation was presumably
315 due to damage of the bacteria by growing ice crystals during the cryo- structuration process
316 (Table S1).

317 3.2 Bioremediation of phenol and cresols

318 Recently we illustrated the bioremediation efficiency of cryogels based on *Pse*, *Rho* and a
319 *Pse:Rho* mixture for 50ppm phenol in carbonate buffer in a dynamic mode (Al-Jwaid et al.,
320 2018). In this study phenol and m-cresol bioremediation by Cryo-*Rho*, Cryo-*Pse*, and Cryo-
321 *Acn* cryogels was examined in dynamic and static mode in MSM buffer (50 ppm (40 mL) and
322 compared with bacterial suspensions (Fig. S5(D) and S6). Suspensions of bacteria of *Pse* or
323 *Acn* degraded 50 ppm (40 mL) of phenol in 7 days (166h), whereas *Rho* completed the

324 degradation in 9 days (220h)(Fig. S5(D)). Increasing the phenol concentration to 100 ppm
 325 resulted in 39.5 % phenol degradation by a suspension of *Acn* over 220h (bioremediation
 326 efficiency 0.123 mg/L/h). *Rho* formed a biofilm on the glass surface in the solution of phenol
 327 (100 ppm, 200 mL), and did not degrade phenol over 12 days of incubation (data not shown).
 328 CBR-*Pse*, CBR-*Acn* and CBR-*Rho* were more efficient for phenol degradation compared to a
 329 suspension of equivalent bacteria(Table 1). Bacterial suspensions of *Pse* or *Acn* degraded 50
 330 ppm (40 mL) phenol in 166h, whereas *Rho* completed the degradation in 220h (Fig. S5(C)).
 331 Cryogel *Pse*-Gel (0.5%) showed slow bioremediation of m-cresol (300ppm), with 21%
 332 degraded over 17 days in a static mode. The presence of polysaccharide Gel in the structure of
 333 the cryogel decreased the bioremediation efficiency of the material, which might be related to
 334 its consumption as a source of carbon. A cryogel composed of a combination of *Rho*, 0.13% of
 335 PVA-al and 0.5% Gel was not as effective for phenol bioremediation as cryo-*Rho* PVA-al-Gel
 336 (1.0:0.3%) (Fig. 4A). Other polymer compositions were used for cryogels preparation based
 337 on PEI-PVA-GA(1:1:0.25%); PEI-PVA-GA(0.6:0.5:0.25%), CHI-GA(1:0.25%) (Fig. 4B),
 338 which revealed complete bioremediation of m-cresol (50 ppm) in 116 and 225h, respectively.
 339
 340 **Table 1.** Bioremediation efficiency (mg/L/h) of cryogels(1mL) and suspensions of bacteria
 341 *Pse*, *Rho* and *Acn* for Phenol(Ph), m-cresol and 4CP for the 1st cycle otherwise specified,
 342 volume of solution 40mL otherwise specified.

CBRs prepared within plastic carriers	Bioremediation efficiency, mg/L/h		
	CBR- <i>Rho</i>	CBR- <i>Pse</i>	CBR- <i>Acn</i>
Cresol 50 ppm at 48h	0.0964 ± 0.029	0.234 ± 0.019	0.307 ± 0.064
Cresol 50 ppm at 220h	0.166 ± 0.051	0.535 ± 0.125	0.60 ± 0.10
Ph 100 ppm at 48h, 2 nd cycle	2.18 ± 0.15	2.250 ± 0.166	0.761 ± 0.098

Ph 100 ppm at 48h, 3 rd cycle	1.84 ± 0.089	-	1.860 ± 0.240
Ph 50 ppm at 48h (V 200mL)	0.091 ± 0.021	0.60 ± 0.10	0.363 ± 0.0424
Ph 50 ppm at 120h (V 200mL)	0.468 ± 0.007	0.50 ± 0.01	0.517 ± 0.016
Free suspensions of bacteria	<i>Rho</i> suspension	<i>Pse</i> suspension	<i>Acn</i> suspension
Cresol 50ppm at 120h (V 200mL)	0.0074	-	0.068 ± 0.073
Phenol 50 ppm at 48h	0.028 ± 0.003	0.159 ± 0.080	0.42 ± 0.080
Phenol 50 ppm at 120h	0.213 ± 0.045	0.317 ± 0.080	0.352 ± 0.050
Phenol100ppm at 48h, 2 nd cycle	0.048 ± 0.039	-	0.276 ± 0.044
Phenol 100ppm at 120h 2 nd cycle	0.039 ± 0.011 ^d	-	0.184 ± 0.026
CBRs without plastic carriers	<i>Cryo-Rho</i>	<i>Cryo-Pse</i>	<i>Cryo-Acn</i>
Cresol 50ppm at 48h (V 200mL)	0.086 ± 0.022	0.386 ± 0.086	0.0833 ± 0.099
Phenol 50ppm at 48h	0.371 ± 0.022	0.151 ± 0.020	-
Phenol 50ppm at 120h	0.874 ± 7xE-4	0.237 ± 0.050	-
4CP 50ppm at 48h	-	0.333 ± 0.038	-

343

344 The suspension of bacteria *Acn* produced only 10 % degradation of *m*-cresol (50ppm, 200mL,
345 a static mode) within 12 days. There was no significant difference in *m*-cresol biodegradation
346 by *Pse* and *Rho*. The suspension of *Rho* degraded only 11 % of *m*-cresol (50ppm, 200mL) after
347 12 days (data not shown). The first bioremediation cycle of *m*-cresol (50 ppm, 200mL) by
348 CBR-*Acn* (9×10^6 CFU) was completed within 5 days. The addition of fresh phenol solution
349 (100 ppm, 200 mL) to the CBR-*Acn* instead of *m*-cresol resulted in only 50% consumption of
350 phenol within 8 days, indicating that the same batch of CBR-*Acn* might be utilised for
351 bioremediation of mixed or complex mixtures, but with similar (by structure) contaminants,
352 i.e. it can be acclimatised to a new contaminant, however it took a longer time compared to the
353 model system(Fig. 4C).

354 The bioremediation of the *m*-cresol was slower over the first 90h of testing for the three
355 bacteria cryogels of cryo-Rho-PEI-PVA-GA, cryo-Rho-PEI-PVA-GA and cryo-Rho-CHI-GA
356 due to bacterial acclimatisation prior to *m*-cresol consumption (Fig. 4B). Bioremediation with
357 CBR-*Rho* and CBR-*Pse* consumed 71% of *m*-cresol (40 mL, 50 ppm) after 10 days (Fig. 4C).
358 The bioremediation using CBR-Rho at higher *m*-cresol concentrations (40 mL, 100ppm)
359 indicated only a 30% decrease in *m*-cresol concentration(data is not shown). CBR-*Acn* revealed
360 better ability to degrade *m*-cresol compared to CBR-*Rho* and CBR-*Pse*. The 1st, 2nd and 3rd
361 bioremediation cycles of *m*-cresol (50ppm) by CBR-*Acn* were completed within 265, 90 and
362 46h, respectively. Regardless of which bacterial strains were used (*Pse*, *Rho* and *Acn*), the CBR
363 had an adaptation period to phenol and *m*-cresol of 48h and 90h, respectively. CBR-*Acn*
364 showed the best degradation efficiency for *m*-cresol among the studied bacterial strains.

365 Following this, the bioremediation process was scaled up in a static mode, and the volume of
366 the solution was increased to 200 mL, revealing a significant decrease of concentration within
367 100-120h for the studied bacterial strains(Fig. 5). The biodegradation of phenol by CBR-*Pse*,
368 CBR-*Rho* and CBR-*Acn* was studied with addition of a fresh portion of phenol after each

369 bioremediation cycle. CBR-*Pse* and CBR-*Acn* consumed 60ppm of phenol within 200h
370 whereas CBR-*Rho* completed the bioremediation in approximately 100h for the first cycle. It is
371 important to note that CBR-*Pse*, CBR-*Rho* and CBR-*Acn* revealed similar phenol degradation
372 activity for following 2-10 cycles, which were completed within approximately 60-65h (Fig
373 S6(A-C)). To the best of our knowledge there is still no information about the efficiency of
374 *Rho* to degrade phenol, cresols and chlorophenols. *Pseudomonas spp.* has been previously used
375 for bioremediation of benzene and toluene into phenol and cresol (Tao et al., 2004 and 2005).
376 Calculation of degradation efficiency showed that CBR-*Pse* caused a more rapid
377 bioremediation of phenol compared to CBR-*Rho* or CBR-*Acn* (Fig. 5 and Table 1). CBR-*Rho*
378 needed an acclimatisation period of approximately 48h before the bacteria became active for
379 bioremediation. CBR-*Pse*, CBR-*Acn* and CBR-*Rho* were more efficient for phenol degradation
380 compared to a suspension of equivalent bacteria (Table 1) and phenol bioremediation
381 efficiencies were 0.6, 0.363 and 0.0915 mg/L/h (48h), respectively (Fig. 5). It can be concluded
382 that the selected strains *Pse*, *Rho* and *Acn* preferably degrade phenol while the biodegradation
383 of m-cresol took place at least 3 times more slowly (Fig. 4C).
384 Overall, the CBRs show resistance to high concentrations of phenol derivatives and
385 significantly faster bioremediation (Fig. 5 & Fig. S5(A-C)) compared to equivalent suspensions
386 of bacteria in a static mode (Fig. S5(D)). Moreover, the recovery of the bioreactors is
387 straightforward and does not require centrifugation to separate suspensions of bacteria from
388 the aqueous solution, making the whole bioremediation process considerably simpler to apply.
389 The same CBR-*Pse*, CBR-*Rho*, CBR-*Acn* bioreactors were used over 10 bioremediation cycles
390 without showing any decline in activity over more than one month of exploitation,
391 demonstrating the ability for reuse of the material over repeat cycles (Fig. S5(A-C)).
392 As noted above, suspensions of bacteria cannot be used instantly for bioremediation of high
393 phenol concentrations (>60 ppm). An increase in phenol concentration resulted in prolongation

394 of the bioremediation process required for its complete degradation (Fig. 5(A-C)). There was
 395 no delay of bioremediation at high concentrations of contaminant for the 2nd (and following)
 396 bioremediation cycles. MTT assay after 17 days of the bioremediation process showed, for
 397 CBR-*Pse*, a significant increase in bacterial numbers compared to initial numbers (Table 2),
 398 indicating their existence in an exponential growth phase. In contrast, CBR-*Acn* and CBR-*Rho*
 399 showed a decrease in bacterial numbers following treatment (Table 2) indicating that these
 400 bacteria had entered a senescence phase. Based on figure 5 one can assume that 300 ppm is not
 401 the limit for the bioremediation process, however there are few examples where such high
 402 concentrations would be encountered in a real case scenario therefore higher phenol
 403 concentrations were not tested further. Usually the concentration of phenols in waste water is
 404 quite low and adaptation of the CBR is unnecessary, but in cases where faster bioremediation
 405 of high concentrations of phenols (200-300 ppm) is required, CBRs may be pre-adapted to
 406 phenol at concentrations of 25-50 ppm.

407

408 **Table 2.** Number of viable cells in initial cryogel and after 10, 28 and 40(*) days of the
 409 bioremediation process (n=3) estimated using MTT assay. CBR-*Pse* control (without
 410 contaminant) the number of cells was $18.9 \pm 2.5 \times 10^6$ CFU after 10 days in MSM at 4 °C.

Contaminant	2CP,	m-cresol,	m-cresol,	Phenol,	
concentration and Before	40 mL,	40 mL,	40 mL	200 mL,	
volume remediation.	50 ppm	50ppm	100 ppm	300 ppm	
Time point, days	0	10	10	10	28
	Number of viable cells x 10 ⁶				
CBR- <i>Acn</i>	39.7 ± 1.42	10.4 ± 3.12	-	-	17.6 ± 0.96
CBR- <i>Pse</i>	12.2 ± 3.64	-	34 ± 2.54	-	38.1 ± 8.3
CBR- <i>Rho</i>	2088 ± 99	653 ± 64	716 ± 122	453 ± 105	576 ± 52

Cryo-RhoGel 1.0% *	-	70.46±18.6	-	-	-
Cryo-RhoGel 0.5%*	-	76.0±5.5	-	-	-
Cryo-PseGel 0.5% *	-	82.1±10.8	-	-	-
Cryo-PseGel 1.0%*	-	60.8 ±3.4	-	-	-
<i>Pse</i> suspension *	-	46.8±8.8	-	-	-

411

412 Analysis of treated water via HPLC confirmed the absence of phenol or release of its
413 derivatives, such as *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid, hydroquinone, catechol and protocatechuate (Tao
414 et al., 2005; Martínková et al., 2009). A few peaks with retention times in the range of 1 & 2
415 minutes were observed which most probably relate to the peak of the solvent, or to the final
416 degradation products of phenol, possibly tri-carbonic acids. The biodegradation of *p*-cresol
417 performed using suspensions of *Pse* and *Rho* revealed a trace amount of *p*-cresol, and some
418 trace amounts of its derivatives were detected after 2 weeks of bioremediation by suspensions
419 of bacteria *Pse*, *Rho* and the corresponding cryobacteria reactors. The bioremediation results
420 for *p*-cresol and *m*-cresol were comparable. Indirect evidence of the release of tri-carbonic
421 acids was given by a pH shift from 7.1 to 6.5-6.4 which is in agreement with previously
422 described pathways of degradation of phenols and cresols (Kolomytseva et al., 2007).

423 3.3 Biodegradation of chlorophenols

424 Chlorophenols (CPs) are relatively stable products of the biodegradation of triclosan and
425 triclocarban, which are widely used as antimicrobial agents in toothpaste, soaps and detergents
426 and are present in most waste waters (Dhillon et al., 2015). Therefore, the efficiency of the
427 developed Cryo-*Rho*, Cryo-*Pse*, Cryo-*Acn* reactors for degrading various CPs was examined.
428 The viability of bacteria via monitoring of turbidity as well as their biodegradation efficiency
429 for 4CP and 2CP in carbonate buffer and minimum salt media (MSM) at pH 7.2 was estimated
430 (Fig. S7 & S9). Data indicated that bioremediation efficiency for suspensions of *Acn*, *Rho* and

431 *Pse* were negligible (40mL 50ppm 4CP) in carbonate buffer at 48 and 120 h, respectively.
432 Bioremediation efficiencies for suspension of the *Rho* and *Pse* in MSM were 0.044 ± 0.019
433 mg/L/h and 0.032 ± 0.025 mg/L/h (40mL 50ppm 4CP) at 48 and 220h, respectively (Fig. S8).
434 From the cryobacteria reactors tested, only cryo-*Pse* PVA-al or PVA-al-PEI-al showed
435 consistent ability to degrade 4CP (Fig. 6 and Table 1), although cryo-*Rho* showed some
436 degradative
437 The 4CP degradation efficiency was much lower compared to bioremediation efficiencies for
438 phenol or m-cresol using the same bacterial strains. Biodegradation of 2CP (60 ppm) resulted
439 in only a 9% decrease after 6.6 days (Table S2). Control cryogels of PEI-al-PVA-al and PVA-
440 al (without bacteria) did not reveal adsorption of phenols or CPs or self-decomposition of the
441 contaminant within 1000h of incubation in the 4-CP (50ppm) solution (40mL).
442 One can observe that Gel based cryogels cross-linked by magnesium ions were less efficient
443 in the bioremediation process compared to sodium cross-linked physical gel, which may be
444 related to some diffusion restriction, as Gel forms a hydrogel such faster. Estimation of the
445 final concentration of 4CP was performed using HPLC, illustrating that suspensions of bacteria
446 (*Pse* and *Rho*) and cryo-*Pse* and cryo-*Rho* can slowly degrade 4CP (Table S2, Fig. 6). It was
447 observed that *Rho* immobilized within the cryogel structure is capable of degrading
448 chlorophenol without additional sources of carbon. These data indicate that cryo-*Pse* and cryo-
449 *Rho* bioreactors, while less effective for 4CP and 2CP, warrant further study in their application
450 for treatment of waste water from hospitals, which has high concentrations of recalcitrant
451 chlorophenols and their metabolites which require removal.

452 **Conclusion**

453 3D structured bioreactors based on live bacteria, suitable for the bioremediation of a range of
454 phenol derivatives (phenol, cresols, chlorophenols), were prepared by cryogelation in a one-
455 step process, using water as a solvent. The macroporous material consisted of 11.6% live

456 bacteria, 1.2% polymers and 87% voids/ pores. For the first time toxicity levels of novel
457 aldehyde containing polymers – cross-linking agents (PEI-al and PVA-al) were estimated and
458 their suitable combination proposed. The cryobacteria reactors maintain their degradation
459 activity over at least 10 cycles. The efficiencies of cryobacteria reactors of *Pse*, *Rho* and *Acn*
460 for degradation of four concentrations of phenol derivatives revealed complete, rapid,
461 bioremediation in dynamic as well as static mode. Moreover, the developed material exhibited
462 significantly better performance for phenol degradation than recently reported by our group,
463 where the bioremediation of 50ppm of phenol(40 mL) in a dynamic mode was studied (Al-
464 Jwaid et al., 2018). Bioremediation cycles (2nd-10th cycle) were completed within 2.6 days,
465 compared to about 10 days for equivalent cell suspensions. The purification of 200 mL of 300
466 ppm of phenol by *Pse*, *Rho* and *Acn* within cryobacteria reactors took approximately 7 days.
467 The use of plastic carriers showed slightly slower bioremediation of cresols compared to
468 conventional cryobacteria reactors. Overall, six polymers and their combinations were utilised
469 to produce materials for bioremediation purposes using three bacterial strains, the activities of
470 which were tested using four model phenol derivatives. The developed technology preserves
471 the native structure and activity of the bacteria. Cryobacteria reactors have several advantages.
472 Cryogels based on live bacteria can be easily reprocessed after inactivation due to low content
473 of a polymeric cross-linker (<10%) in the structure and therefore the technology can be
474 considered as “green”. There is no diffusion restriction as materials are macroporous with well-
475 developed connected micro channels that improve interaction of the cells with contaminated
476 water. The macroporous structure of interconnected pores also creates the possibility of
477 exploiting the bioreactor as a flow through column or filter system with no requirement to
478 separate the bacteria after the bioremediation process. The technique is faster and simpler than
479 a previously published three-step cryogel surface immobilisation techniques for phenol

480 degrading bacteria, which also contain a large bulk content of polymer resulting in more
481 complex processing after use.

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487

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